

Magnetism, Lorentz Invariance and Addition of a Dimension

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In (1), we suggested that if a rest mass transforms (under a Lorentz transformation) as a 4-vector, leading to a momentum vector p and energy scalar, then the electric scalar potential ϕ (which when multiplied by charge q), which represents energy, should also transform in the same manner, leading to a vector function A (analogous to momentum). Given a starting 4-vector of $(0, \phi)$, A necessarily contains ϕ . A negative gradient is applied to ϕ for a charge at rest to obtain the electric field E . If one has two charges separated by a distance along the y axis, the first charge may be said to exert an electric force on the second proportional to E . As seen from a moving frame, ϕ transforms as a 4-vector, but - gradient should still be applied to the new ϕ to obtain a piece of electric force. This implies that the gradient should also be applied to A which contains ϕ . Thus, force is more complicated as seen in the moving frame.

We note that an idea which emerges in this situation is that if one starts with one dimension, i.e. the y direction, and has motion in the x , a one dimensional problem in the rest frame necessarily becomes a two-dimensional one in the moving frame. This has implications on the forces seen in the moving frame.

We attempt to calculate this force in two ways. First, we note that one cannot create a vector by using grad and A once in the same expression and so try to consider appropriate combinations of the vectors v (velocity), A and grad , with grad acting on A (because it contains ϕ). This leads to the form $v \times (\text{grad} \times A)$ if one insists that d/dy appear in the solution (because the charges are along the y axis in the rest frame.)

The second approach is to use the sum of Lorentz invariants $(1) -Edt+pdx + (A dx - \phi dt)$ as the classical action and to then find the equation of motion using the idea of a stationary path (i.e. the usual Lagrangian approach) to arrive at the same magnetic and electric forces as seen in the moving frame. This requires the notion of retarded time.

Lorentz Transformation

If one is given a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t , one may ask what a person in a frame moving at constant $-v$ (velocity) sees? In (1), we suggested that the basic information of m_0 does not change, but that one may have v or $-v$ for the moving frame, while m_0 has no direction. We suggested creating a matrix using orthogonal row vectors $(x,0)$ and $(0,ct)$ and multiplying it by $m(v)/ct$ where $m(v)$ is the mass as seen in the moving frame (which could in principle be different than m_0). Assuming no change in information, we wrote the equation:

$$\begin{vmatrix} mv/c & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} -mv/c & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_0 \end{vmatrix} \quad ((1))$$

$$((1)) \text{ leads to: } mm_{cccc} = mvmv_{cc} + m_0m_{occcc} \text{ with } m=m_0/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \quad ((2))$$

This leads to the emergence of the concepts of $E=m_{occc}/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ and $p = mv/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$.

It is then possible to create a Lorentz transformation which converts the vector $(0, m_0)$ into (pc, E) .

In another note (2), we suggested that if one has an electric scalar potential ϕ , then $q\phi$ represents energy ($q=\text{charge}$) and so

$$(0, \phi) \rightarrow \text{Lorentz transformation } (A(r',t'), \phi(r',t')) \quad ((2))$$

Here A is a vector function (analogous to p). The transformation acts on functions of r, t in the stationary frame, and so once ϕ has undergone a Lorentz transformation, one must rewrite x, t in terms of x', t' . This indicates that a spherical ϕ in the rest frame will no longer be spherical. We note that: $v=x'/t'$. In the last section, we see that in the Lagrangian approach, one must consider the situation of retarded time.

The Question of the Electric Field and the Emergence of a Magnetic Field

We consider two charges q at rest along the y axis separated by some distance b at a time t . They exert a force on each other. This force is qE , where $E = -\text{grad } \phi$. Thus, the gradient of ϕ is linked with force, but the Lorentz transformation leads to an A which is proportional to ϕ , so grad of A in some manner should also represent a force. The question is how does one exactly perform this operation?

Imagine that the two charge rest frame picture is seen from a frame moving at constant $-v$ in the x direction. The one-dimensional rest picture necessarily becomes a two dimensional one.

Given grad and A , both vectors, one cannot create a vector by using each once in the same expression. One requires another vector and v (velocity) is the only other vector in the problem (proportional to p). In such a case, one wants grad to act on A alone, but the combination of v, grad and A has to be a vector (i.e. force). This yields the possibilities for a constant v :

$$V (\text{Grad dot } A) \quad ((3a)) \quad \text{and} \quad v \times (-\text{grad} \times A) \quad ((3b))$$

Now grad must make use of d/dy because this derivative creates the full force in the rest frame. V is $(v_x, 0, 0)$, and $A = (A_x, 0, 0)$ so $((3a))$ does not contain d/dy and must be dropped.

$((3b))$ on the other hand yields: $v \times (0, dA/dz', -dA/dy')$ which contains the required dA/dy' , but also dA/dz' .

Thus, there seems to be a piece of extra force, linked directly with velocity, given by $-\text{grad} \times A$. (This is in fact the magnetic field.)

In the moving frame, the electric field is no longer simply $-\text{grad } \phi$, but we use another approach to find $v \times B$ again and the full electric field expression.

The Lagrangian Approach

In the previous section, we used (x, y, z, t) to represent the rest frame and (x', y', z', t') to represent the situation seen from a frame moving with $-v$. Here, we use the variable (x, y, z, t) to represent

the situation seen from the moving frame and let $v = (v_x, v_y, v_z)$, where v_x is the x component of v etc.

In (2), we suggested creating the sum of two energy Lorentz invariants and called these the action density:

$$L dt = -E dt + p dx - q \phi dt + q A dx \quad ((3))$$

It is known that $-Et + px$ is the classical action (both relativistically and nonrelativistically) for $v=x/t$, so we suggest that ((3)) is $L dt$. Then:

$$L = \text{Lagrangian} = -E + p \cdot v - q \phi + qv \cdot A \quad ((4))$$

Thus, using the stationary property of the Lagrangian:

$$p_{full} = dL/dv \text{ partial} \text{ and } d/dt p_{full} - dL/dx \text{ partial} = 0 \text{ so}$$

$$P_{full i} = p_i + q A_i \quad ((5a)) \text{ and } d/dt p_i + d/dt q A_i - q \text{ grad } \phi - q v \cdot dA/dx_i \text{ partial} = 0 \quad ((5))$$

We also introduce the idea of retarded time, following (3).

In (3), one has a charge distribution given by a charge density over r'' (vector), a fixed origin and a fixed measurement point given by the vector r (measured from the origin). Then:

$$\phi = C_1 \int dv'' \text{ charge density}(r'' \text{ vector}, t-R/c) / R \quad dv'' \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{where } R = |r \text{ vector} - r'' \text{ vector}|$$

This leads to a result where $\phi(r \text{ vector}, t)$ is really a function of $r \text{ vector}$ and $t - |r \text{ vector}| / c$

$$\text{where } |r \text{ vector}| = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \quad ((7))$$

In the previous section, $x' = vt'$. Here we use x in place of x' , so:

$$x = v_x t, \quad y = v_y t \text{ and } z = v_z t \text{ where } v_x \text{ is the x component of } v \text{ etc } ((8)).$$

$$\text{Then: } dA/dt = dA/dt \text{ partial} + v_i dA/dx_i \quad ((9))$$

Thus: the A dependent terms yield, for the i component of force

$$dA_i/dt \text{ partial} + v_j dA_i/dx_j - v_j \cdot dA_j/dx_i \quad ((10))$$

Mathematically, the last two terms are equivalent to: $v \times (\text{grad} \times A)$ i.e.

$$\{ \mathbf{v} \times (\text{grad} \times \mathbf{A}) \} = \epsilon_{ijk} v_j \epsilon_{klm} \partial_l A_m \quad \text{where } \partial_l = d/dx_l \text{ and } \epsilon_{ijk} \text{ is the Levi-Civita symbol}$$

$$= v_j \partial_i A_j - v_j \partial_j A_i \quad ((11))$$

Thus, one may introduce a new E field (as seen in the moving frame) and a $\mathbf{B} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{A}$ such that

$$\mathbf{E} = -\text{grad} \phi - \partial \mathbf{A} / \partial t \quad ((11a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{B} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{A} \quad ((11b))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we use the notion of a Lorentz transformation applied to a rest mass, creating a momentum and E, to an electrostatic energy $q\phi$, (q =charge) creating a transformed $q\phi$ and a vector field \mathbf{A} (which is a function of ϕ). If $\text{grad} \phi$ leads to a component of force, as seen in the moving frame, then grad somehow acting on \mathbf{A} , must also create a component of force. We note that if the electrostatic force is between two q charges along the y axis, and one views this system from a frame moving along the x axis with a constant velocity $-v$, then one converts a one-dimensional problem into a two-dimensional one. One must combine grad with \mathbf{A} , both vectors, to create a vector with grad and \mathbf{A} only appearing once. This cannot be done, so one must introduce another vector. The only other vector is \mathbf{v} , which may create a vector with grad acting on \mathbf{A} as: $\mathbf{v} \cdot (\text{grad} \times \mathbf{A})$ or $\mathbf{v} \times (\text{grad} \times \mathbf{A})$. In the electrostatic case, the force is obtained using d/dy , so this must also appear in the moving frame case, but $\mathbf{v}=(v_x,0,0)$ so $\mathbf{v} \cdot (\text{grad} \times \mathbf{A})$ is ruled out, leaving $\mathbf{v} \times (\text{grad} \times \mathbf{A})$ as piece of "new" force. One may call $\text{grad} \times \mathbf{A}$ the magnetic field.

We also use two Lorentz invariants, $-E dt + p dx$ and $-\phi dt + \mathbf{A} \cdot d\mathbf{x}$ to create an action density L and apply the stationary principle to obtain $\mathbf{E} = -\text{grad} \phi - \partial \mathbf{A} / \partial t$ and $\mathbf{B} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{A}$, which is consistent with the $\mathbf{v} \times (\text{grad} \times \mathbf{A})$ piece found above.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Relativistic Momentum/Energy from Information and Space-Time (preprint, zenodo, 2024)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Relativistic Momentum/Energy from Information and Space-Time Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2024)
3. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory. Addison-Wesley 1980. Pp 458-459